

Sequential Niching Particle Swarm Optimization Algorithm for Localization of Multiple Damage Locations using Fiber Bragg Grating sensors

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Abstract

Structural Health Monitoring (SHM) systems have a potential to reduce lifecycle costs of structures through maintenance planning and lifetime extension. Hence, there is a lot of active research in the area for SHM of civil and mechanical structures. The SHM system should be low cost, suitable for continuous monitoring, able to detect small levels of damage. Guided waves (GW) based SHM techniques allow monitoring of large thin-walled structures with a few sensors and have been identified as the most promising of techniques for SHM. The GW based techniques allow mapping of damage very easily, and hence are a powerful tool for assessing the damage. The mapping of damage with high resolution is of course computationally expensive and hinders real-time decision making. Hence, methods are being developed to minimize the processing time.

In this paper, the authors implement a sequential niching particle swarm optimization (PSO) for multiple damage detection. It is shown that the niching PSO is able to detect multiple damage scenarios effectively. The processing time is significantly better (order of magnitude) hence making it suitable for real-time assessment. The paper also presents some sensitivity studies, for determination of the thresholds. The validation has been conducted experimentally on an aluminum plate instrumented with piezo-actuators for actuation and FBG sensor for sensing. The results indicate that the niching PSO is suitable and indeed a better alternative than the brute-force techniques commonly used in literature.

Keywords: Guide waves (GW), optimization, actuator, FBG sensors, Niching PSO,

1. Introduction

Structural health monitoring (SHM) of critical structures is mandated by law in most countries. The SHM improves safety and reliability of the structure while reducing maintenance costs. The potential return on investment of SHM systems is 13.1 times [1]. Thus, it has been subject of a lot of interest from energy, marine and aerospace sectors. The

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most commonly used SHM techniques are the vibration based SHM [2], strain based techniques [3], guided waves (GW) based techniques [4], electromechanical impedance (EMI) based techniques [5] etc.

The GW based techniques are ideal for thin walled structures such as plates, and pipes as they allow fast monitoring of large areas with relatively few sensors. Also, as the sensitivity of the method is directly related to the wavelength, even small damage may be detected using GWs. The use of GW for isotropic metallic structures is quite extensive [6]. But the application for composite structures remains a challenge due to the high attenuation and non uniform wave propagation profile. In spite of these challenges GW remains a promising tool for composite structures and extensive work in this area is being carried out [7].

Lead zirconate titanate (PZT) based actuators and sensors have been used for the actuation and sensing of GWs for a long time. In addition to the PZT, some other contact based techniques such as macro-fibre composites (MFC), as well as non-contact techniques such as electromagnetic acoustic transducers and lasers etc. have been used in the literature for actuation [6]. The above mentioned actuators can also be used for sensing. But some other techniques such as laser Doppler vibrometer or optical fiber sensors may be used as well. The optical fibre based sensors offer several advantages such as small size, light weight, ability to be multiplexed, insensitivity to magnetic and electric fields etc. and are considered very attractive for GW sensing applications. An excellent overview of the different optical fiber based sensors for GW sensing has been given in [8].

The use of **fiber Bragg grating (FBG) sensors** with the wavelength division multiplexing (WDM) was proposed more than 20 years ago [9] and is considered as a mature technology. Unfortunately, the WDM configuration does not allow the sensitivity and the sampling rate necessary for GW sensing. For the GW sensing, the FBG sensors need to be applied in the so-called edge filtering configuration. The edge filtering approach has been explained in detail [10]. The high reflectivity slope is used to amplify the signal and modulate in terms of change in amplitude. Through the use of photo-receiver and oscilloscope, a high sampling rate may be achieved. At the same time due to the steep slope of the reflectivity spectrum an advantage is achieved leading to an increased sensitivity and resolution. This increased sensitivity and resolution can be leveraged to achieve better damage detection even in the case of multiple damage locations on the structure.

Guided waves have been commonly used for damage detection and localization. The two commonly used approaches are the tomographic approach and the time-of-flight approach. The tomographic approach needs a very dense grid of actuators and sensors. This is very challenging to achieve with the FBG sensors due to their passive nature. Hence the time of flight (TOF) approach needs to be used. The TOF based approach analyses the wave arrival for each actuator sensor pair and maps the damage location based on the difference using the elliptical approach or hyperbolic approach [11]. The plate is discretized into pixels with the desired resolution and the damage index (DI) is calculated for each of the pixels for each actuator-sensor pair. The final super-imposition of all the pairs over the entire structure allows identification of the hotspots which indicate damage location. This calculation of DI at each pixel leads to additional computational and delays in the determination of the condition of the structure. So more efficient techniques need to be developed. Balasubra-

maniam et al. [12] used a multi-step technique to reduce the number of pixels for which the DI needs to be computed. Although significant improvement in the time was achieved, the applicability of the method is limited, as the method requires a circular placement of the actuators and sensors to divide the structure into sectors. Soman et al. [13] used the particle swarm optimization (PSO) for the determination of the damage location and reported a 66% improvement in the processing time. But the implementation of the PSO restricts the detection and localization of the damage to one most severe location. In many cases, more than 1 damage may be present on the structure, the PSO based localization will not yield all the locations of damage. Hence a new technique for the localization of multiple damage locations is needed.

Furthermore, the problem of the detection of multiple damage scenarios without a priori knowledge of the number is very difficult. The determination even in the case of brute-force based technique depends on the determination of appropriate thresholds, which are subjective. To the best of the author's knowledge no technique for the detection of multiple damage scenarios using evolutionary algorithms have been developed. This paper aims at addressing this lack of research. The paper develops a sequential niching PSO algorithm for the localization of multiple damages. The number of damage locations on the structure is not a priori known. The framework is applied on an aluminum plate with PZT actuators and FBG sensor at the middle. Multiple scenarios (with 1, 2 or 3 damage) are analyzed and the damage are localized. The framework of the methodology for the detection of multiple damage scenarios using evolutionary algorithm is the main novelty of this paper. The methodology is applied on a simple aluminum plate with different number of damage locations.

The rest of the paper is organized as follows: in the next section the methodology including the implementation of the niching PSO is provided. The section 3 shows the experimental setup used for the validation of the proposed methodology. The next section presents the results of the localization and compares the performance of the method with the brute-force based technique. The section 5 draws some conclusions based on the results presented and identifies the areas of future work.

2. Methodology Overview

2.1. *Damage Mapping*

The common practice for damage mapping using the ellipse-based approach is the pixelated approach, where the structure is discretized in pixels and the damage indicator (DI) for each of the pixels is computed based on the time of arrival (TOA). This approach is called the brute-force approach. Different DIs have been proposed in the literature such as the exponential approach and its variations [13], ellipse of uncertainty [14], number of ellipses [15] etc. In the course of our previous study the exponential approach was shown to outperform the number of ellipses approach and hence will be implemented. The DI is given by equation 1

$$D(x, y) = \sum_{i=1}^{N_p} \exp\left(-\frac{t_{exp} - t_{th}}{\tau}\right) \quad (1)$$

where $D(x, y)$ is the damage index at a particular pixel, N_p is the number of actuator-sensor paths, t_{exp} is the time of arrival determined experimentally, t_{th} time of arrival for the pixel determined theoretically. and τ is a sensitivity factor. This DI has to be computed for each pixel of the grid which makes it computationally expensive. In order to limit this computational effort, meshless technique based on particles have been proposed [13]. The chosen DI has been shown to be very robust and has been applied on a range of different measurement techniques (LDV, PZT and FBG sensors) as well as range of different materials including honeycomb as well as carbon and glass fiber composites [12, 16].

For the meshless techniques the damage localization problem is treated as an optimization problem. An objective function is determined and then existing mathematical optimization tools are used to obtain the optimal solution. Particle swarm optimization (PSO) is a meta-heuristic technique which is easy to implement and needs very few initialization parameters. PSO involves a swarm of candidate solutions which are determined by their position and velocity. The position is the location in the search space and the velocity is the parameter that allows traversing of the particle in the search space to allow global search. The interaction of the particles with its own previous locations and the best performing locations yields PSO algorithms an element of swarm intelligence not found in other evolutionary optimization techniques such as genetic algorithms. The PSO has found many applications indifferent fields including parameter identification [17], topology optimization [18], damage detection [19] etc. Ghannadi et al. [20] present an overview of all the papers using PSO for damage detection. There are only a handful of papers which deal with the multiple damage scenarios, but none of the papers formulate the PSO where the number of damage locations is not known which highlights the novelty of the presented work. Also it is noteworthy that in none of the papers covered in [20], the niching is used, which too is novel. For a 2D localization problem, the PSO is ideally suited and has fewer artificial constraints. This allows a more thorough search of the possible solution space and efficiency in the implementation. Due to its simplicity and efficiency, the PSO was chosen as the algorithm for the optimization in this paper. Ofcourse the conventional PSO will only yield the global optimum and will not be able to detect multiple damage locations. As a result, a sequential niching PSO is implemented to allow the localization of multiple damage locations. A point to note, that there are potentially other means of localizing multiple damage scenarios besides niching, such as the Bayesian approach by Fakhri et al [21]. But these techniques, have not been applied for such studies, have no inherent mechanism to ensure that all the locations will be detected and are not as computationally efficient as considerably more computational effort is required for the population generation as compared to the PSO.

2.2. Sequential Niching PSO and its implementation

The PSO is an extremely well known algorithm and the details have been discussed in detail in [22]. Niching is defined as the process of separation of individuals according to their

states in the search space or maintenance of diversity by appropriate techniques [23]. This can also be used for determining multiple optimal solutions in the search space. Several different techniques can be applied for achieving niching such as the the parallel technique, the sequential techniques, dynamic fitness sharing, clustering [24] etc. The sequential niching is easy to implement and hence was chosen for this application. The flowchart for the sequential niching of PSO employed in this work is given in Figure 1.

Figure 1: Flowchart of sequential Niching PSO.

The boxes in blue color are specific to the niching functionality of the PSO and will be discussed in detail here. The other components of the PSO are quite standard and interested readers are referred to [13] for detailed explanation. Dummy values for the global fitness ($G_{fitness}$) and global best ratio GB_{ratio} are initialized. The values are taken as 0.1 and 1 respectively for this study. But any other value significantly smaller than the global maxima is acceptable for the $G_{fitness}$ and any value greater than equal to the limit value (0.85) is acceptable for the GB_{ratio} . Then the sequence loop is initiated and once the $GB_{ratio} \geq limit$ is valid the PSO is initialized. The cost function is a combination of the DI and the weighing function proportional to the proximity of the particle position to the global bests identified in the previous sequences. The weighing function 'G' was determined using the [code provided](#)

in appendix A.

The variable 'distlist' gives the distance between the particle position and all best positions (optimum from each sequential run). If the distance of the particle from any of the optimas is less than the variable 'distlim' an extremely low value of the weighing factor is assigned. This makes the solution not attractive for the algorithm and is not chosen as the global optimum anymore. The closer the particle to a previous identified global maxima, the lower the weighing function. The 'distlim' value was set based on the accuracy expectation from the damage localization algorithm and was set as 4 cm in this case. The product of the DI and the weighing factor give the cost function of the PSO. The maxima of which is determined iteratively over several iterations to obtain the optima. Once the end conditions in terms of convergence or number of iterations are reached, the $G_{fitness}$ list and the GB_{ratio} are updated and the sequence number is updated. The next sequence is then run once again till the inequality for the GBratio does not hold. As the last run of the PSO yields 'GBratio' which is not above the threshold limit, the last identified optima is not identified as a damage location. The niching PSO was implemented in MATLAB using the parameters shown in Table 1 . The parameters were chosen based on the experience of the authors from the previous work [13]. [The different parameters namely the co-efficients influence the quality of the global search and the convergence to the optima. An excellent discussion on the choice of the coefficients is given in \[25\].](#) The stopping ratio determines the condition where the sequential runs are stopped while the influence ratio determines the region where the weighing around optimal solutions from previous runs is applied.

Table 1: Parameters for niching PSO

Parameter	Value
Momentum coefficient	0.05
Global best acceleration coefficient	0.5
Personal best acceleration coefficient	0.1
Gradient acceleration coefficient	0
cut-off criterion	0.1
Max iterations	10
Swarm size	200
Global best stopping ratio	0.85
Global best influence radius	4 cm

3. Experimental Setup

In order to validate the methodology experimentally, an aluminium plate(0.5m \times 0.5m \times 0.001m) was instrumented with actuators and sensors as shown in Figure 2. The sensor was in the middle of the plate, and actuators were at 12 cm from the sensor at every 30° angle from 0° to 180°. The positions were determined as part of another study [26] related to the directional sensitivity and the authors did not have any control on their locations. Multiple damage scenarios (total 8) were introduced using additional mass in the form of magnets. [The magnets \(2 cm in diameter\) are attached on either side of the plate \(total](#)

Figure 2: Schematic of the experimental setup

15g weight) and held firm due to the attraction even with the aluminum plate in between. The additional masses is a convenient way to introduce reversible discontinuity (damage) in the structure and is a commonly used strategy. Furthermore, the use of additional mass has been shown to be equivalent to a drilled hole [27]. In addition to the sample, a tunable fiber coupled laser (Apex AP1000) was used for generating a wavelength centered on the positive slope of the reflectivity of the FBG (Femto Fibertech). A pre-amplified photodetector (Menlo Systems, FPD610-FC-NIR) was used for detecting the change in the optical power which was acquired using an oscilloscope (National Instruments, PXI 5105). For the excitation, 5 cycle Hann windowed signal at 50 kHz was generated using the arbitrary waveform generator (National Instruments, PXI 5413). The signal was amplified 100 times using a signal amplifier (Krohn-Hite,model 7500) and supplied to the piezo actuator(CTS corporation, NCE51). The measurements were averaged 50 times to suppress the measurement noise. The frequency chosen was based on the excitation characteristics of the PZT used. At the chosen frequency, the A0 mode is far more dominant than the S0 mode. As a result the signal processing is much easier. The method can be easily extended to other frequencies. The main aim of this work was to validate the niching-PSO and hence the studies with different frequencies is considered beyond the scope of this paper. The 8 damage scenarios were chosen, 3 with single damage location, 3 with two damage locations and 2 with 3 damage locations. The nomenclature and the locations are shown in the Table 2.

4. Results and discussion

4.1. Damage localization using Niching PSO

The Figure 3 shows the progression of the maximum fitness and the mean fitness for the entire population convergence for the 2 sequential runs of the niching PSO for case Sc4. It should be noted that for the sake of presentation the stopping number of iterations were

Figure 3: Convergence of niching PSO over 3 sequential runs

relaxed from 10 to 20 for this plot. The following observations can be made, the convergence close to the global minima was achieved around iteration 8, so the choice of 10 iterations is enough to obtain the global minima. Also, the average fitness is getting closer to the global minima, which means that the PSO is indeed improving the swarm fitness. For the third run, the stopping criterion was achieved after 7 iterations. The global ratio condition was not satisfied and the sequential runs of the PSO were terminated. This indeed shows that the niching algorithm works appropriately. The final spread of the niching PSO for the run 1 and run 2 are shown in the Figure 4

Table 2: Damage scenario details

Scenario	damage list	damage coordinates [cm]
Sc1	D1	(35.1, 19)
Sc2	D3	(19.8, 30)
Sc3	D5	(19.5, 25)
Sc4	D1, D3	(35.1, 19); (19.8, 30)
Sc5	D1, D2	(35.1, 19); (12.8, 12.8)
Sc6	D3, D4	(19.8, 30); (39.5, 40)
Sc7	D1, D3, D4	(35.1, 19); (19.8, 30); (39.5, 40)
Sc8	D1, D4, D5	(35.1, 19); (39.5, 40); (19.5, 25)

(a) Run 1

(b) Run 2

Figure 4: Damage localization results for Sc4 (black circle shows, damage location, the blue dotted circle shows acceptable region for damage localization, red particles shows the swarm, the filled circle shows the global best solution) a) run 1 b) run 2 (x and y axis show the coordinates of the plate in cm)

(a) Run 1

(b) Run 2

Figure 5: Damage localization surface maps with pixel approach for Sc4 (black circle shows, damage location, the blue dotted circle shows acceptable region for damage localization, red particles shows the swarm, the filled circle shows the global best solution) a) run 1 b) run 2 (x and y axis show the coordinates of the plate in cm)

For the purpose of damage mapping, the whole plate was divided into a mesh of 100×100 pixels (discretization). The Figure 5 shows the cost function at each pixel for the two runs. Firstly, both the damage locations are clearly identified by the brute force approach in the run 1. The run 2 surfaces are shown just to show the effectiveness of the weighing parameter based on the proximity to the global solution. The maximum value achieved in the surface plot was 5.439, while that in the PSO was 5.588. This difference is around 3% and caused due to the limited resolution of the pixel based approach. The PSO particle can take any real value and hence is better suited for the determination of the true global optima. In order to minimize this error a more denser mesh is necessary which will increase the computation time significantly.

The Figure 6 shows the population progression for all iterations for scenario Sc1. As can be clearly seen the damage is localized effectively.

The localization results for the other 6 scenarios are shown in Figure 7. As can be seen multiple damage are successfully detected and localized. So it can be concluded that the niching algorithm works effectively.

4.2. Sensitivity studies and Comparison of performance

The PSO is a meta-heuristic technique, and there is no guarantee about the convergence, also each run has the potential of detecting a slightly different optimal solutions. In order to show the repeatability, the algorithm was run 100 times for the scenario Sc4. The results are presented in Figure 8a. As can be seen, only two runs yield the damage location outside of the acceptable zone, this shows that indeed the PSO based detection has a very high accuracy. Another point to note is that the order in which the two damages are detected changes, this is a function of the meta-heuristic nature of the PSO. The other sensitivity study run was for the determination of the threshold of the GB_{ratio} , the value determines the potential for the missed damage localization or wrongful identification of damage. The actual value is determined based on the trade-off between the possibilities of this mis-classification. As a missed detection has may lead to worse outcome it is better to aid on the side of caution. The threshold was changed from 1 to 0.75 at intervals of 0.05 for scenario Sc6 and is shown in Figure 8b. As can be seen for the threshold 1, only 1 damage D4 was detected. For threshold 0.95, D4 and D1 are detected. For threshold 0.9, 0.85 all three damages are detected and hence these are potential candidates for the threshold. When the threshold is lowered further, more locations are identified as damaged which is not true. Hence these candidates (0.8, 0.75) are not suitable. Among the two suitable candidates 0.85 was chosen as appropriate. This choice is made as it is more disastrous to miss a damaged location than falsely detecting a location as damaged when it is not.

In addition to the sensitivity studies, some comparison was performed. The authors in their previous work [13] have shown that the exponential ellipse based approach is superior than the number of ellipses as the cost function. This is due to the better resolution in terms of the cost function one may achieve. So, in this case the computational performance was compared for the 8 cases and is shown in Table 3.

As can be seen, the number of computations necessary are considerably smaller than the brute-force. The iterations column shows the number of iterations needed for each sequential

Figure 6: Swarm locations at each iteration for Sc1 (black circle shows, damage location, the blue dotted circle shows acceptable region for damage localization, red particles shows the swarm, the filled circle shows the global best solution) (x and y axis show the coordinates of the plate in cm).

(a) Sc2

(b) Sc3

(c) Sc5

(d) Sc6

(e) Sc7

(f) Sc8

Figure 7: Damage localization results for other 4 scenarios (black circle shows, damage location, the blue dotted circle shows acceptable region for damage localization, circles show general particles, x shows optimal solution, the colors are different for each run to ensure maximum visibility) a) Sc2 b) Sc3 c) Sc5 d) Sc6 e) Sc7 f) Sc8 (x and y axis show the coordinates of the plate in cm)

Figure 8: Sensitivity Studies a) damage localization results for 100 runs for Sc3 (black circle shows, damage location, the blue dotted circle shows acceptable region for damage localization, o show the first optima obtained, x shows the second optima obtained) b) damage localization results for different threshold values for Sc6 (black circle shows, damage location, the blue dotted circle shows acceptable region for damage localization, o shows the optimal solutions obtained) (x and y axis show the coordinates of the plate in cm)

Table 3: Computational performance

Scenario	Brute-force		PSO		
	computations [-]	time [s]	iterations [-]	computations [-]	time [s]
Sc1	25001	1113.56	6, 6	2400	7.45
Sc2	25001	1008.64	10, 6	2600	6.52
Sc3	25001	1032.83	10, 10	4000	8.30
Sc4	25001	1075.22	10, 10, 7	5400	12.62
Sc5	25001	830.95	10, 10, 7	5400	8.45
Sc6	25001	851.61	10, 7, 6	4600	10.46
Sc7	25001	768.72	6, 10, 10, 10	7200	13.15
Sc8	25001	864.87	10, 10, 6, 7	6600	12.86

run to achieve the convergence criterion of the PSO. The number of sequential runs is one larger than the number of damage locations in the structure. The number for the brute-force is corresponding to the damage resolution one needs, but for the PSO, as the encoding is real valued, the resolution is theoretically infinitely small but in-reality 0.01 due to the rounding up. The resolution achieved is still 10 times better than the one with brute-force technique. Although the number of pixels is same for the brute-force the time required depends on the number of peaks identified in the experimental signal for each actuator-sensor pair. Furthermore, for the worst case (sc7) the number of computations is only 70% less but the savings in time are 98% better. This is due to the memory allocation and the trouble with handling large amounts of data. This difference will increase with the increase in the resolution which will result in even bigger matrices. The measurements were compared on the same computer without any parallelization and hence the saving are considered not affected by external factors or implementation limitations. Lastly, the niching PSO performance can be further improved by incorporating parallel niching techniques, which will be investigated in the future.

5. Conclusions

The paper provides a proof of concept of a standardized method using niching PSO for localization of multiple damage scenarios. A sequential niching PSO is implemented and applied for localization of 1, 2 and 3 damage locations on an aluminum structure. To the best of the author's experience this is the first such implementation for multiple damage scenarios using GW and is the main novelty of the paper. The parameters for the PSO have been chosen based on engineering judgment to ensure a thorough global and local search. Also, the threshold criterion for the sequential runs is experimentally determined, and validated. The PSO indeed allows the damage localization in significantly lower time as opposed to the brute force algorithm while improving the damage resolution. It should be conceded that the study is applied for the proof of concept on a simple aluminum structure. More studies on anisotropic structures, need to be undertaken before the above technique may be used for damage localization in real structures and is identified as an area of future work. Also, the PSO being meta-heuristic has no guarantee of giving the optimal results, although 2% error is acceptably low (compared to 10% probability of detection standard used in the aerospace industry [ref]), a multi-objective optimization may need to be developed to improve the reliability. [The multi-objective optimization may allow focussing on two different metrics which are a function of the presence of damage rather than just one used here \(reflection from a discontinuity\).](#) [The use of multiple objectives will allow overcoming of systematic errors in the system \(symmetric placement of sensors\) or measurement errors.](#) Also, as there is possibility of detecting more optimas, it has a potential to be applied for reference-free damage localization in particular the instantaneous baseline based algorithms. The imperfect subtraction of baseline, usually leads to a high damage index for the direct arrival path, which can be overcome through the niching approach. This too will be investigated in the future.

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Appendix A. Code for assigning weight based on proximity to previous global solutions

```
1 distlist=pdist2(coords , bestpos);
2 if any(distlist(:) <= distlim)==1
3     G(1,1)= min(distlist(:)/distlim)^10;
4 else
5     G(1,1)=1;
6 end
```

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